

RESEARCH ON THE CREATION OF A STRUCTURE WITH AN ACTIVE WORKING DEVICE FOR A BASE LEVELER

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Annotation. *The article covers the current and capital leveling of land, the types of machines during leveling and the work performed by them, machine brands, the resistance forces falling on the machine during operation, advantages and disadvantages of basic levelers, and issues of their improvement.*

Key words: *technique, technology, land leveler, machine, capital leveling, current leveling, irrigation, level of flatness, milling machine, repeated watering.*

The decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated March 29, 2023, Presidential Decree No. 103 "On additional measures to encourage the provision of modern agricultural equipment to the agricultural sector" was adopted.

Decision to implement the necessary agrotechnical measures in the production of agricultural products in a timely and qualitative manner, to meet the demand for agricultural machinery in the agrarian sector, to replace agricultural enterprises with modern and resource-efficient equipment aims to improve the system of incentives for the provision of techniques.

Today, the role of the agricultural sector in the national economy of the country is very important. 63% of the country's population lives in rural areas. 35% of the employment of the working population corresponds to agriculture.

Uzbekistan ranks 6th among the world's cotton-producing countries. The standard of living of the population of our country, and its material well-being depends on the progress of economic reforms in agriculture, and the speed and efficiency of its development. In this case, the owners of farms take care of the land, treat it in a timely and high-quality manner, and observe all agrotechnical measures is an important factor in the life of the farm.

Increasing the efficiency of the production of agricultural products in our country is inextricably linked with the development of rural infrastructure. After all, raising the quality of the economic and social infrastructure in the villages to the level of modern requirements will not fail to have a positive effect on the development of the country today.

As the President noted, there is a link between the rural economy and social life, as well as in politics, through which the entire republic can achieve

prosperity and prosperity. It is difficult to imagine the production of agricultural products without irrigated lands because we get more than 90% of our crops from irrigated lands. Therefore, the problems of irrigation and land reclamation are crucial for us. Since Uzbekistan is a country specializing in a large agricultural production complex, land reclamation and productivity are of crucial importance. The productivity of lands is mainly related to their irrigation and conservation. In this regard, our state has been implementing both legal and practical measures since the first days of independence.

To ensure the implementation of Presidential Decree No. 3459 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh. Mirziyoyev "On additional measures to further increase the level of technical equipment of agriculture", mechanization of agriculture of our republic, farmers To increase the productivity of agricultural products obtained from crops, extensive scientific and innovative works are being carried out aimed at the application of modern techniques and technologies, which imply the effective use of modern science and technology achievements, and the improvement of existing ones.

Currently, available levelers are low in efficiency. These levelers have low maneuverability, consume a lot of metal and consume a lot of energy, and work efficiency is low. To solve these problems, it is necessary to improve the working bodies of levelers. Usually, basic land levelers cut and level the surface of the ground at a depth of 4-5 cm in one pass. The resistance in this alignment is very high. As a result, the leveler's work speed and quality decrease, and productivity decreases. Clay and wet sands stick to the walls of the tub, so the performance of the leveler decreases. When working with dry sands, the use of basic levelers will be ineffective, because the traction force will not be enough due to the free engagement of the tracks with the sand. Taking into account the above, it is urgent to improve the work efficiency of levelers.

Leveling of irrigated lands creates conditions for increasing the productivity of agricultural crops, preventing labor costs and excessive wastage of water during irrigation, high-quality processing between rows and high-quality harvesting by machines. . As a result of several times tilling and watering the soil, unevenness of the field of various shapes is formed, that is, long ridges and furrows in the process of plowing, high-lownesses and residual unevenness of the previous year are formed after watering. . In addition, in certain parts of the field, the soil settles and sinks due to repeated watering. It is recommended to eliminate such irregularities by current (exploitation) leveling. On leveled lands, agricultural machines work with high productivity, the salt of the land is washed well, the seeds fall to the same depth, their germination is even and complete, and 6-7 percent of water is saved.

Capital leveling works are carried out in the summer in fields freed from winter wheat or in autumn before the main plowing, and current leveling works are carried out after the end of plowing. Capital leveling works cannot be carried out in all fields at the same time, so these works must be carried out in a planned manner.

The accuracy of leveling of the surface of the fields is ± 5 cm. should not exceed, i.e. ± 5 cm in the fields. It is necessary to level all the corners higher than in uneven lands, germination is prolonged due to seeds falling to different depths, plant growth is different, their demand for water and fertilizer is not the same, the ripening of pods is delayed, and the yield is reduced.

Moisture is evenly collected everywhere in the leveled fields, the soil is prepared at the same time, the seedlings are fully harvested, and the cotton is treated with quality between the rows.

However, in the unlevelled field, until the soil of the lowlands reaches maturity, in other places, the soil dries up due to rising moisture, and the cultivator cannot soften such lands to the same depth.

The ridges and ridges formed during plowing, as well as the ridges and ridges formed during the plowing of the turns of the field and the burial of the remaining parts of the ditches, are lost during the current leveling..

The current leveling is carried out in two stages: First of all, the margins formed by plowing are leveled and the gates and bumps are buried, this work is done only in the fall. It is absolutely impossible to leave the land leveling work performed in this first stage until the spring, because in the spring when a lot of moisture accumulates in the soil, if the land is leveled, the soil will become denser.

In the second place, before planting the seeds, the surface of the entire field is leveled.

GN-2.8 and GN-4 type graders are used in the first stage of leveling work, in the second stage VP-8, VP-5, KZU-0.3 type levelers, MV-6.0 type leveler-grind levelers are used. It is not possible to use various "pipes", electric poles, and other devices instead of a mola.

When the areas of the irrigated fields are leveled, good conditions for uniform wetting of the soil are created and the irrigation rate is reduced. Two types of leveling are used in lands to be meliorated: initial (rough) and main types. During the initial leveling, the topography of the field is leveled: ridges are cut and pits are filled. This work is done with bulldozers, graders, or scrapers. To level the microrelief of the earth, basic leveling is carried out with the help of long-base and combined levelers. Due to such leveling, unevenness of the field up to 10 cm is eliminated.

Earth leveling mechanisms and their use.

The earth leveling mechanism (or leveler) is a tool that has been used since ancient times and is still widely used today due to its simplicity and efficiency.

This mechanism is used for the following purposes:

- leveling and softening of the earth's surface;
- dividing the upper layer of the earth into smaller pieces;
- improvement of extraction of the surface layer of the earth;
- fight against weeds growing on the ground;
- densification of the earth's surface (at a certain depth);

- grinding hard pieces of earth;

The advantages of such a machine are:

- has a simple and solid structure;
- it is not necessary to have special knowledge to use;
- ensures that the surface of the earth is taken uniformly;
- ensures the formation of a special soil layer that prevents the evaporation of underground water;
- can also be made by local craftsmen.

The disadvantages of such a mechanism are:

- binds moist soil and reduces its water absorption properties;
- the ground becomes slightly denser;
- small particles of soil come to the surface and holes appear under this layer;
- movement speed is limited;

With a leveler, the depth of tillage in harder soil can be adjusted by adding additional weight, special coupling, or travel speed. In many cases, the expected effect can be achieved by passing the tools several times. In wet soils, it is necessary to find a balance between sufficient leveling works and measures to prevent the aggregation of soil particles. For the activities carried out with the help of a leveler to be effective, ground leveling must be done at a certain angle to the direction of the previous processing.

System for connecting and controlling the earth leveling mechanism to the tractor.

Most of the earth-level machines and mechanisms are manufactured as towed vehicles. A hook system with a mechanism panel is used to connect the leveling machines to the tractor. The pull angle, as well as the working depth and power, can be changed by lengthening or shortening the hook attachment and choosing a higher or lower coupling.

Control and adjustment of the earth leveling mechanism.

Processing the ground with such a mechanism depends not only on the structure of the leveler but also on the following factors:

- the weight of the leveler (taking into account the additional weight);
- traction angle;
- the angle of the transverse plane
- movement speed.

Leveling is one of the main factors in improving the reclamation condition of irrigated areas in agriculture. The yield of all agricultural crops in leveled areas increases by up to 40%, water consumption in irrigation is reduced by 2 times, and the productivity of the agricultural machinery used in the future increases, working conditions are improved. It is known that current and exploitation leveling of land in irrigated areas is carried out annually in short periods of 25...30% of the total land area of farms in autumn and spring before planting long-base P-2,8A, P-4, PA-3, PPA-3,1 and other brands of ground levelers are operationally leveled.

If land leveling works are carried out according to agrotechnical requirements:

- agricultural machines work with high productivity in leveled fields;
- the salt of the land is washed well;
- the seeds fall to the same depth;
- sprouts sprout evenly;
- a full seedling is taken;
- 6-7 percent of water is saved.

- Moisture accumulates evenly everywhere in the leveled fields, the soil is prepared at the same time, the seedlings are fully collected, and the cotton is treated with quality between the rows.

If land leveling is not done on time:

- in an uneven field, until the soil of the lowlands reaches maturity, in other places the soil dries up due to rising moisture, and the cultivator cannot soften such lands to the same depth, which means:

- lowers the quality of work;
- large lumps appear on unsoftened lands;
- soil moisture evaporates quickly;
- the plant does not develop well.

Capital (main) and current leveling works are carried out in agriculture to eliminate land irregularities.

capital (main) leveling is carried out once in 3-4 years.

current leveling is carried out after plowing.

As a result of smoothing, the following results are achieved:

- In a flat area, the irrigator irrigates 1.5-2.0 hectares in one day;
- A tractor operator performs 1.5-2 normals of work in a day when planting seeds and working between the rows on a leveled field;
- Work productivity increases;
- On well-leveled areas, high-quality saline is washed, water consumption is reduced, and full seedlings are obtained. Irrigation works are carried out in good quality, soft soil is formed in cultivation;
- consumption costs are reduced.

if not transferred

- In uneven areas, the irrigator irrigates 0.5-0.6 hectares in one day;
- It will be difficult for the tractor operator to fulfill the specified norm on uneven fields;
- Low work productivity - leads to delaying of agricultural activities;
- Saline washing is carried out with poor quality;
- For this reason, sprouts germinate unevenly, the number of seedlings decreases;
- It hurts productivity.

Although levelers are simple in appearance, they are very complex in terms of operation and technology, and their efficiency depends on the size of the area unevenness, and several other factors. In addition, their maneuverability

is very low, their metal capacity is large, they are not adapted to supply other agricultural machines, and they consume a lot of power in the process of work. Many scientific researches have been carried out in Central Asia to justify the rational operation technology of tall levelers. It was found in scientific research that as a result of the levelers passing over the same place many times, the top layer of the earth becomes denser and hardens, and the productivity of the unit decreases. These defects are almost abundant, especially in small-contour lands. Tests showed that (for example, the P-4A leveler) the volume of work in the first pass is 300 m³/ha, and after the fifth pass, the volume of work is 104 m³/ha. To determine the efficiency of the levelers according to the number of passes, the average value of non-texture was determined.

The main sharp decrease in unevenness occurred after the 1st and 2nd passes, and the unevenness almost did not change in the next passes. Taking into account the above, the number of passes should be reduced from 6...7 times to 1..2 times.

table 1

The average value of non-textiles, mm	Brand of straighteners			
	PA-3	D-719	P-2,8A	P-4A
Until the 1st transition	8,1	137	83	118
The first after the transition	62,5	85	62	81
Second	53	72	58	71
Third	5,3	6,9	5,9	7,3
Fourth	50	-	64	74
The fifth	52	-	65	71

When the thickness is 10..12 cm, it is necessary to pass the plot along both diagonals once. The main criteria for the efficient operation of levelers: are quality of work, productivity, and the amount of money spent per unit of work performed.

According to the results of scientific research, the average size of irregularities in the Bukhara region is 15..30 m in length and 20..40 meters in width, and the average length of unevenness in plots with an average contour (3..5 ha) is 7 ...11 m, the average height of unevenness is around 10..15 cm. The analysis of the above-mentioned plains shows that, compared to medium and large contoured sections, the size of the non-textures on the small contoured sections is different. From this, it can be concluded that the level of flatness is higher in small contoured lands than in medium and larger ones. If we use long ground levelers in areas with small contours, the corners and turning points of the plots will not be leveled. Because the base of these levelers is 15..16 m, the turning radius is up to 15..20 meters, the productivity is low due to low maneuverability. Taking into account this and the scientific work and experience of specialists, it is possible to use grader levelers GN-2,8A and GN-4A aggregates in small contour areas. However, the base of these levelers is small, so the quality of work does not fully meet the requirements of agrotechnics.

Therefore, we believe that it is effective to use small levelers in areas with small contours.

Picture 1. Structural scheme of the device with a softening milling cutter for a long leveler.
1 - milling softener, 2 - axle with milling cutters installed, 3 - spindles, 4 - supporting column holding the axle, 5 - device frame, 6 - hydraulic cylinders that raise and lower the milling device, 7 - hydraulic motor, 8 - drive chain transmission

As we know, the land is being leveled with long-base levelers. But when leveling the land, various plant roots and large lumps appear. This affects the quality of the plane. To solve this problem, we aimed to increase the quality of leveling and the efficiency of the work by placing the work equipment with a milling softener in front of the leveler (picture 1).

2 - picture. Structural scheme of the device with a softening milling cutter for a long leveler.

1 - milling softener, 2 - axis with milling cutters, 3 - spindles, 5 - frame of the device, 6 - hydraulic cylinders that raise and lower the milling device

The working technological process of the smoothing milling device is as follows: during the forward movement of the long leveling unit, the milling device is brought to the working position with the help of a hydraulic cylinder. The milling cutters rotate around their axis, cutting and softening a certain layer of soil in front of the plow and crushing various plant roots and residual stems, large pieces.

Softened and fragmented cuttings, shredded roots, and residual stems are formed in front of the leveler bucket, and a larger amount of soil pile is placed in the leveler bucket, the resistance of the leveler bucket blade to shearing the soil is reduced, and at the same time, the soil pile is fully spread over the width of

the bucket, resulting in the leveling quality of the field. increases. The milling cutters are installed on two opposite sides of the same axis, with the milling cutters facing each other. Rotary motion is transmitted to the mills using hydraulic motors and chain transmissions. As a result of using a milling device on a long leveler, the resistance of the blade of the leveler to shearing the soil is reduced, and the quality of leveling increases by crushing large lumps, roots, and residual stems.

The working technological process of the smoothing milling device is as follows: during the forward movement of the long leveling unit, the milling device is brought to the working position with the help of a hydraulic cylinder (6). The milling cutters (1) rotate around their axis (2) to cut and soften a certain layer of soil in front of the plow and grind various plant roots and residual stems, in large pieces. Softened and fragmented cuttings, shredded roots, and residual stems are formed in front of the leveler bucket, and a larger amount of soil pile is placed in the leveler bucket, the resistance of the leveler bucket blade to shearing the soil is reduced, and at the same time, the soil pile is fully spread over the width of the bucket, resulting in the leveling quality of the field. increases. Milling softener (1) are installed on two opposite sides of the same axis, with the milling cutter facing each other. Rotational motion to milling cutters (1) is transmitted through hydraulic motor (7) and chain transmissions (8). As a result of using a milling device on a long leveler, the resistance of the leveler blade to cut the soil is reduced, and the quality of leveling increases by crushing large lumps, roots, and residual stems.

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